

International Association for Media and Communication Research

IAMCR 2021 Nairobi - Participatory Communication Research Section (PCR)

Exordo Submission ID #719

IAMCR
NAIROBI2021

Research Paper

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Abstract

For people with Intellectual Disability (ID), participatory and inclusive research is a matter of human rights and an increasing concern. Nevertheless, in the field of games, approaches are mainly framed in medical perspectives, linked to the notion of assistive technology, neglecting a sociocultural view of digital media (Sousa, 2020). Although research with this population poses inherent and complex practical challenges (Coons & Watson, 2003), changing the paradigm of approaching the relationship between digital media and ID, from therapy to co-creation, can be a very relevant step in the path for media participation and, ultimately, social inclusion of these individuals. In this paper, we present the insights from a participatory approach in the context of game creation, involving 30 university students (Bachelor's Degree in Videogames) and 14 institutionalized adults with ID, with 12 of them also having motor disabilities. This represents a comprehensive and player-centric approach, which differs from those normally used in the field of serious games. Therefore, instead of starting from the needs of people with ID perceived by third parties, such as doctors, therapists, or family members, the games were developed based on the interests and needs of these individuals, perceived and verbalized by themselves. One focus group about interests and media habits, nine co-creation sessions with feedback gathered from the target audience, and three playtesting rounds were conducted, between March 2020 and January 2021. This process resulted in 10 accessible games for people with ID, created considering their interests, needs, cognitive and motor characteristics, as well as in a different tangible interface (controller) for each game, adapted to their motor impairments. The ethnographic study of this creative process, based on participant observation, highlights the potential role of digital games and participatory game development processes in the promotion of empowerment and self-determination of people with ID. This study also stresses the importance of tightening the bond between academia and civil society organizations, such as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) of people with ID, to foster social change through participatory media creation and inclusive learning processes for students.

Keywords: Participatory Research; Games; Intellectual Disability; Inclusion; Accessibility; Empowerment.

When an individual plays a good, well developed game, they move towards the most positive end of the emotional spectrum, through intense engagement that fosters the physical and mental conditions required for all kinds of positive emotions and experiences. Gameplay potentially activates different cognitives systems - including attention and memory - as well as it supports emotional induction and rewards systems (McGonigal, 2011). Moreover, play is the first cognitive strategy of human beings, therefore crucial to explain and understand the world, allowing exploration, experimentation, and consequently learning (Frasca, 2009). Games can be therefore seen as having inherent meaning making processes, framing them as ways to convey values, and opening a wide range of possibilities for the individuals within the gameplay. Thus, games allow individuals to complement the linear visions provided by other forms of narrative, through the manipulation of several simultaneous variables (ibid).

Even though, as discussed above, games seem to be a space of cultural expression, meant to provide rich and positive experiences through interaction and meaning making, for individuals with disabilities this tends to be interpreted through a much more limited and categorical lens (Wästerfors & Hansson, 2017). For example, a Systematic Literature Review that intended to analyse the studies approaching games and disability, produced and published between 2010 and 2020, concluded that

individuals with ID tend to have a passive role in games research, with gaming mainly seen through therapeutic frameworks, neglecting recreation and representation as crucial factors (Sousa, 2020). More specifically, individuals with ID were generally requested to play a game chosen by the research team, with only 16.7% ($N = 9$) of the studies including them in the choice process, either through the collection of their interests and needs or through participatory design approaches (ibid.).

The tension that contextualizes the present approach was previously presented by Kafai & Burke (2016), specifically aimed at learning, through the dichotomy between instructionist and constructionist gaming. Highlighting the role values play in games as learning environments, the authors support the notion that serious gaming can also support exclusion, as it does not necessarily guarantee diversity. To better understand specific groups and contextualize them in terms of values is crucial, to avoid the perpetuation of stereotypes, and the maintenance of inequities. Therefore, while instructional gaming can consider interests and experiences, constructionist gaming recognizes these experiences as a path for participation and making, supporting players to creatively and critically engage with games (Kafai & Burke, 2016). In the presented study, besides the centrality of interests and experiences, accessibility needs are seen as a crucial path for a more constructionist gaming approach, considering the very specific cognitive and motor characteristics of the audience.

Considering this, this study aims to answer the need for participatory processes in media creation studies, specifically targeting the scenario of games and ID. By targeting a population with very specific needs, the proposed research also discusses games' accessibility as a priority, and a matter of inclusion.

Methodological Considerations

As a methodological approach to Participatory Action Research (PAR) within gameplay and game creation, the 'in-game', 'in-room', and 'in-world' model (Stevens, Satwicz, & McCarthy, 2008) was adopted. Therefore, instead of analysing playing games as an activity that occurs in a somehow separate world, we acknowledge that it has a context and is always connected to the individuals' daily lives and cultural practices. Playing games is inherently situated and connected with all the three dimensions ('in-game', 'in-room', and 'in-world'), while the dimensions are also connected between them (Stevens, Satwicz, & McCarthy, 2008). The first two dimensions were analysed through the collection of systematic observation insights during the different steps of the study, including co-creation sessions, playtestings, and game sessions. The 'in-world' dimension was more related to the potential changes in individuals after this process, and was operationalized through a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators, collected before and after this process. This included items from the Self-Evaluation Wellbeing (SEW; CRPG, 2010), the Personal Results Scale (Simões et al., 2017), the Support Intensity Scale (SIS-A; Lopes-dos-Santos et al., 2020), and others specifically developed for the study.

To better operationalize PAR, the entire creative process with the students was documented, as well as, the subsequent playtesting and gaming sessions with people with ID, in a logic of participant observation and through an ethnographic approach, which allow the study of this form of media as a complex process of meaning construction, socially and contextually situated (Schröder, Drotner, Kline, & Murray, 2003). For this, a systematic observation grid was filled in each co-creation, playtesting, and gaming session.

With the students/developers, the adopted approach intended to foster both accessibility practices and inclusion related beliefs, through the process of participatory game development. Such approach was framed on the notion of experimental game design, as introduced by Waern & Back (2015, p.342), as a strategy "to elicit something interesting about design principles for games" - in this case cognitive and motor accessibility. To assess this strategy, an open-ended questionnaire was conducted, before and after the process, accompanied by the application of the Community Living Attitudes Scale (CLAS-ID; Henry, Keys, Jopp, & Balcazar, 1996).

Participants

The present study had two groups of participants: adults with ID, and students from the Bachelor's Degree in Videogames. The sample was composed of 14 people with ID, from a NGO that supports this population. Eleven (78.57%) lived in the institution (in a fully supported home system), while the other three (21.43%) spent their days in the institution, but lived in their own homes, with support from family. People with ID in the sample were aged between 30 and 64 ($M = 46.21$; $SD = 9.27$), being ten males (71.43%), and four females (28.57%). Considering the assessment details provided by the institution, all the participants were characterized as having severe ID, which we interpret in light of the notion of support needs. Therefore, all of the participants had relative autonomy, but constant need for supervision. Eight participants (57.14%) also had motor disabilities, ranging from the inability to autonomously use one of the hands to spastic tetraplegia. Seven participants (50.00%) used a wheelchair to move.

Thirty university students participated in the process, but only 17 provided valid answers to the applied questionnaires. From this 17, 12 were males (70.6%), two were females (11.8%), and three (17.6%) preferred not to answer. The students were aged between 19 and 25 years old ($M = 21.12$; $SD = 1.62$). Most of the students had no contact with people with ID ($N = 15$; 88.20%). The two other students (11.80%) stated that they have people with ID in their families.

Procedure

As above explored, in the present study a participatory approach to the development of accessible games by students was implemented. The games were developed over two semesters, with the first semester being dedicated to the concept and production of the test prototype. In the second semester, the prototype was tested with the audience, the game was finalized, and the controller was produced.

The concept phase began with a session on the interests, cognitive, and motor characteristics of the target audience, led by the researcher that was in constant and direct contact with the audience. The game concept and gameplay principles, developed with the assistance of the subject professors, were discussed and validated in two sessions interspersed in time, also with the researcher and considering the feedback provided by people with ID. The first semester ended with the finalization of the game prototype and the second semester started with the respective playtesting, recorded on video, by people with ID. This video registration was essential for the students/developers to meet the interests and accessibility needs of the audience. By being confronted with the cognitive and motor needs of people with ID, students were able to better design controllers adjusted to these needs.

Through this procedure, one focus group about interests and media habits, nine co-creation sessions with feedback gathered from the target audience, and three playtesting rounds were conducted, between March 2020 and January 2021.

Since people with ID were considered a high risk population for COVID-19 transmission, direct contact between students/developers and people with ID was not possible as initially planned. Nevertheless, one focus group about interests and media habits, nine co-creation sessions with feedback gathered from the target audience, and three playtesting rounds were conducted, between March 2020 and January 2021. Although pandemic restrictions did not allow for direct contact, it was clear that the various moments of feedback and video documentation brought a participatory nature to the game development process that not only led to a production that was more adjusted to their needs, but also raised the students' awareness of inclusion issues.

During game creation, more than developing for a specific target, students were also challenged to develop games that can be interesting for everyone, even if containing specific accessibility options and features.

Preliminary Insights and Results

The preliminary results obtained from the presented approach can be organized into three different, yet complementary, groups: the developed games; the results of the empowerment of people with ID; and the pedagogical value of the process for the involved students.

Games

Ten games were developed through this process, nine digital games and one hybrid game (analogical with an electronic interface). The games presented great diversity in terms of genres, including one party game (*Adivinhas?*), one first person shooter (*Chicken Shooter*), two simulations (*Canoe* and *FlyYouBirds*), two arcades (*Orbiter* and *Space Conqueror*), one endless runner (*Endless Runner*), one casual game (*Virtual Companion*), two puzzles (*Futebolástico!* and *SoundQuest*).

With the professors' sensibilization and through their empirical conclusions, game developers/students mainly adopted an approach with a small number of inputs (2/3) to support accessibility, and progressively realized that the possibility to customize in-game options, such as speed or number of opponents was crucial to the success of their work.

Still in the field of accessibility, one of the main insights of this approach is related with the need to rethink concepts frequently applied to game design, such as 'spacing effect' (Hodent, 2018), considering the cognitive specificities of people with ID. In this specific case, the results from the observation of the playtesting and gaming sessions pointed to a need to adopt a more progressive approach to the introduction of game mechanics, namely considering different premises regarding memory and learning. The combination of different mechanics introduced only after several levels seemed to be a good approach to this question.

Every game had a controller specifically developed for it, serving a double purpose: enhancing games' motor accessibility, considering the characteristics of the audience, and enhancing engagement through the creation of a tangible interactive product that is aligned with each game's aesthetic. Examples can be seen in Figures 1, 2, 4, and 5.

Figures 1 and 2. Gameplay screenshot and tangible interface of *Space Conqueror*

The digital games' art frequently adopted classic games aesthetic trends, like pixel art. Even if no specific indication regarding art was given to the students, this result is highly relevant, as it can foster a discussion about the democratization of these aesthetic elements, to populations whose play experiences are closely linked to interactive therapeutic resources, that are typically less rich in this field, and privilege realism-driven instead of fantasy-driven art.

Another interesting trend observed in some games is the desire to provide people with ID with sensory experiences that are not frequent in their daily lives (e.g. walking on the rain in *Endless Runner*) or that can provide a certain notion of freedom (e.g. driving a boat in *Canoe* or flying in *FlyYouBirds*). This seems to be related with the perceived needs of the players, and exponentialized by the heavy lockdown that adults with ID living in residential facilities faced during the pandemic.

As in previous experiences, the inclusion of this approach in a graded, mandatory Bachelor's subject poses some barriers, with some students lacking interest to continue the improvement of their games, after the end of the subject, difficult the development of finished products, ready to disseminate online.

Empowerment of People with Intellectual Disability

Considering the already analysed results of the applied quantitative scales, people with ID showed significant superior results in empowerment and well-being related items, namely connected with

decision-making and personal development. The triangulation of these results with the content analysis of the systematic observation grids, bases one of the most crucial insights of the present approach. The development of empowerment in the people with ID seemed to be more linked with the game development and playtesting process, than with the gaming itself. The players frequently state that it is relevant to them to see the changes they suggested in the new versions of the games, or the problems they found solved. One player, for example, frequently reinforced their perception of being relevant to the process, through quotes like “I have been a great help” or “this was what I said was wrong and now it is not wrong anymore”. This was recurrent in different players, usually the ones that showed higher scores in engagement related items from the quantitative measures.

The role of this process in fostering decision-making as an empowerment factor, can also be linked to the design of the process, with both playtestings and gaming sessions conceived to promote choices and feedback. During these sessions, questions like “What do you want to play?”, “How do you want the game to be?”, or “Would you like it to be a little slower?” were recurring.

The role of games in introducing new activities and experiences in the daily lives of people with ID was also shown, either through the players’ engagement in the sessions or through the constant requests to anticipate them (“I know we scheduled tomorrow, but can we play today?”). This must be discussed considering the interactive characteristics of games, but always considering the novelty factor that was introduced, to contradict the institution’s lethargy, reinforced by the pandemic situation. An interesting insight of the present study is that, designing studies involving games for people with ID, namely institutionalized adults with severe ID and consequently high support needs, challenges the researchers’ and developers’ preconceived notions of gaming knowledge. As individuals working with games on a daily basis, it is easy to assume that everyone possesses basic games and digital literacy skills. Some individuals in the sample were not familiar with the mechanics of pressing a button (keeping it pressed indefinitely, for example), which forced the approach to be constantly redesigned to include time and support in the acquisition of such literacies. This is also seen as an inclusion-driven approach that can support the civic engagement of individuals with ID in a highly digitized society.

Even with higher barriers to engaging in gaming, the participants frequently showed behaviors and verbalized thoughts that support the development of a stronger sense of competence and ability, from learning the controls of a game to achieving better results in each gaming session. We can hypothesize that this sense of competence is emphasized in this population, considering that the society tends to overprotect them, decreasing their chances to sense achievement.

Pedagogical Value

Regarding the pedagogical value of the present approach to the game developers/students, it was relevant in two different levels: the development of accessibility related skills and the decreasing of discriminatory beliefs towards individuals with ID.

Through the analysis of the student’s expectations (before the process) and feedback (after the process) it was clear that the notion of accessibility implementation in games was much more developed. The specific measures stated by the students in the post-process questionnaire included adaptation of difficulty, usage of visual communication, adaptation of the number of inputs, among others. More than knowledge on how to develop games for people with ID, some students seemed to develop a broader notion of accessibility, showing other concerns, like with players that are not able to hear, to see, or to distinguish colors. One student stated that “this concern should always be somehow present, since people with ID can be part of any target audience”, and other student even suggested the creation of a system for games that, as Pan European Game Information (PEGI) does for age, could certify its accessibility to different audiences.

Moreover, considering the results from the application of CLAS-ID (Henry et al., 1996), students showed lower levels of discriminatory beliefs toward people with ID, adopting attitudes more in line with the principles of empowerment and community inclusion.

Both results can be seen as relevant for the development of better professionals in the future that can truly incorporate accessibility-driven practices into their work, while fostering inclusion and representation in the games industry.

Discussion and Future Directions

In the present short paper, we briefly present the main insights from the proposed approach. This is framed in a broader set of qualitative and quantitative indicators, processed through statistical and content analysis, to achieve more developed conclusion and future directions for the intersection between game studies and critical disability studies, through a participatory, playercentric lens. Nevertheless, it is possible to argue that the ethnographic study of this creative process, based on participant observation, highlights the potential role of digital games and participatory game development processes in the promotion of empowerment and self-determination of people with ID. The process provided an opportunity for these people to break the lethargy in which they usually live, through a chance to see their voice heard and translated into a media object.

Considering the above-discussed preliminary results, it is relevant to emphasize a data-based criticism to the notion of 'serious' games. This criticism is centered around the concept and how it contradicts itself to some extent, bringing together two terms that are opposite - serious and playful (Hodent, 2018). Therefore, this approach acknowledges the relevance of considering games mainly as playful experiences, even if an outcome external to the game world is targeted, in this case empowerment. Through the future studies of the produced games' long-term usage, regarding learning and cognitive outcomes, such as digital skills or executive functioning, it will be possible to understand the feasibility of a different framework for the development of the so-called 'serious' games. This framework starts in the player, framing their interests and needs, basing game development and, only in the endline, hypothesizes the potential skills targeted, as presented in Figure 3.

Figures 3. Proposed participatory model for game development

This model is more in line with the concept of constructional play (Kafai & Burke, 2016) and at the same time with the current inclusive research premises for people with ID (Coons & Watson, 2013; Kramer, Cohn, & McDonald, 2019). It works within an empowering perspective, that considers games also as a cultural expression, besides their learning or clinical value. Such model, may not present immediate or even measurable results in cognitive or learning outcomes, but opens new recreational and playercentric perspectives for the relationship between people with ID and games, that connects also this media to the premise of "nothing about us, without us" that originated the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD; United Nations, 2006) and most activist movements in the field (Johnson, Hopkins, & Minogue, 2019).

An example of the centrality of player's interests in the game development process is the case of *Futebolástico!*. This game can be clearly described as a labyrinth reskinned as a soccer field (Figure 4 and Figure 5). Contrary to our expectations as games researchers, this was one of the games that

better engaged the players. Even if the same players frequently developed paper and pencil labyrinth based cognitive stimulation activities in the institution, and reported low interest for them. This example can be better understood by the notion of ‘playworld’ as presented by Frasca (2009), that considers the game world as composed of all the elements of the experience, including not only the mechanics, but also all the aesthetical and narrative elements.

Figures 4 and 5. *Gameplay screenshot and tangible interface of Futebolástico!*

So two different games, with the exact same mechanics, can generate different meanings, emphasizing games’ rhetorical potential, even for individuals that tend to struggle with meaning making processes, like people with ID. Moreover, through these processes, games contradict the mainstream development premises, and can even be seen as triggering a political and ideological intervention to some extent (Flanagan, 2009). Future studies can also explore the subversive type of reskinning for people with ID, or other disabilities and specific needs.

Even if providing several insights that can help shape the future of the field, some limitations must be considered and discussed. The participatory process was heavily conditioned by the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic. The low access to the institution only allowed the direct interaction between one of the researchers/professors and the subjects, with no direct interaction between the students and the players, as initially planned. Although several efforts were developed to ensure that the voice of the people with ID was listened to by the game developers/students, this process was mainly mediated, which can cause different biases. Moreover, game sessions were developed with only one participant at the time, and not in groups as planned, which obviously conditioned the observation of relevant ‘in-room’ behaviors, namely associated with social interaction, like ‘backseat gaming’. The number of game sessions was also smaller than what was initially planned, considering that the same schedule had to accommodate 14 different individual sessions, instead of four group sessions.

The lack of digital access of the study’s sample of individuals with ID, with only one computer for playing the games available and only in the psychologist’s room, severely conditions the feasibility and long term impact of the process. It does not allow that play happens spontaneously and through intrinsic motivation processes, conditioning a fully independent play experience also through the constant intervention of a therapist or caregiver (Pitaru, 2007). Nevertheless, the developed games will be made available online, through a Creative Commons License, hoping this increases their effective autonomous use by people with ID, and any other potential players. Plans to support the production of the tangible interfaces in a FabLab will also be available online.

The conclusions of the present study, namely regarding the skills related to games accessibility that were promoted in the students, stress the importance of tightening the bond between academia and civil society organizations, such as Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) of people with ID, to foster social change through participatory media creation and inclusive learning processes. This contact between game development students and people with ID can work as a strategy to foster the development of more accessible games, as well as for the problem of the lack of representation in the games industry (Malkowski & Russworm, 2017).

Indirectly, the present approach also based the discussion around media accessibility in a broader way, as a strategy to address the digital divide. By including people with ID in a game common to

most people - playing games, we can hypothesize an increase of media literacies, also supported by participatory media creation.

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